

Proposal for Change

BBMRI-ERIC Directory data structure changes

Executive Summary

In this document we propose a couple of changes to the data model of the BBMRI-ERIC Directory. Most of these changes are structural changes to make it easier for the National Nodes to fill in the data in the Directory and limit duplication of data.

Rationale

Information in the Directory should be relevant for its users and easy to collect and record for the biobanks that are listed in the Directory. This proposal suggests removing a couple of items that were not used and addresses a couple of issues with the data entry to reduce the administrative load for the biobanks and reduce the support load for the Directory team. Where applicable a replacement is available that provides a better way to record the data.

Proposed Changes

We propose changes to the Biobanks, Collections and Network tables. The Biobanks table records the administrative data of a biobank, and the Collections table records the information about the samples and data in the biobank. Currently no changes to the structure of the other tables in the Directory are proposed.

In all three tables there are the attributes **longitudinal and latitudinal data**. This to create a location spot on a map.

The outcome of the quality check report was that a lot of these attributes were not or wrongly filled in.

We propose to delete the longitudinal and latitudinal field and replace it for a field called location where people can fill in the name of the city. This change requires changes to the way that the National Nodes record and a change in the script of the map of biobanks.

The collections table includes data about **access policies**. People have to fill in if an access fee is needed, if the access is only for joint projects, a description of the access and a weblink. At the moment collections holders have to fill it in three times. Four questions for samples access, four questions for data access and four questions for imaging data access. Boolean questions. The existing data in the directory shows that when people fill in more than one access policy (samples, data or imaging), weblinks and descriptions are the same.

We propose to replace the booleans for categoricals Mrefs. The Mrefs are linked to a table with the categories sample, data, imaging. Also delete $\frac{2}{3}$ descriptions and weblinks. Via this way people have to fill in 4 attributes instead of 12. This change requires changes to the way that the National Nodes record and publish data to the Directory.

The collections table also includes data about **sample and data management**. People have to fill in if there is a PD/SOP for processing, transport or storage. At the moment collections holders have to fill it in two times, three questions for samples, and three boolean questions for data.

We propose to replace the booleans with categoricals Mrefs. The Mrefs are linked to a table with the categories sample processing, sample transport, sample storage, data processing, data transport, data storage. Via this way people have to fill in one attribute instead of six. This change requires changes to the way that the National Nodes record and publish data to the Directory and changes to the Directory application.

Impact

The changes have impact on both the Directory application and the integration of the National Node databases with the Directory.

The Directory team must perform the following steps:

1. Update the structure of the Directory database schema
2. Update the Directory application to be compatible with the database schema
3. Update scripts for publishing data, quality monitoring, etc. that is dependent on the database schema
4. Support the National Nodes in making the relevant changes in their systems
 - a. For the National Nodes that use the MOLGENIS system (NL, DE, BG, BE) we need to write migration scripts to update the database and documentation on how to perform these changes.
 - b. For the other National Nodes we need to provide documentation of the changes to the database schema
 - c. Update the Data Manager manual

The National Nodes must update their systems to accommodate the changes. It depends on the infrastructure of the National Nodes what must be done.

The changes need to be coordinated between the Directory team and the National Nodes. In order to avoid disruption we need to work out a two-step process, where the new structures are added before the structures that they replace are removed and where the removal of the old structures is done after a short transition period agreed with the National Nodes.

Appendix 1 – List of changes

A summary of all the changes can be found in the following table.

Table	Field	Action	Explanation	Impacts application	Impacts NN Data Publishing
Biobanks	location	ADDITION	We will replace the longitude and latitude fields for a text field, locations, where you can fill in the city name	No	Will be ignored
Biobanks	longitude	DELETE	No longer necessary when the field location is active	No	Will be ignored
Biobanks	latitude	DELETE	No longer necessary when the field location is active	No	Will be ignored
Networks	longitude	DELETE	Delete because networks can have more locations	No	Will be ignored
Networks	latitude	DELETE	Delete because networks can have more locations	No	Will be ignored
Networks	location	ADDITION	We will replace the longitude and latitude fields for a text field, locations, where you can fill in the city name	No	Will be ignored
Collections	longitude	DELETE	Delete because the location of the samples is an internal matter of the biobank, so the location of the biobank is enough	No	Will be ignored
Collections	latitude	DELETE	Delete because the location of the samples is an internal matter of the biobank, so the location of the biobank is enough	No	Will be ignored
Collections	location	ADDITION	We will replace the longitude and latitude fields for a text field, locations, where you can fill in the city name	No	Will be ignored
Collections	access_fee	ADDITION	We will replace the acces_fee fields for a Mref field, access_fee (without sample,data or image), A new table "access" is needed (see below). Here you can chose : sample,data, imaging)	Yes	Will be ignored
Collections	access_joint_project	ADDITION	We will replace the access_joint_projects fields for a Mref field,access_joint_projects (without sample,data or image), A new table "access" is needed (see below). Here you can choose : sample,data, imaging)	Yes	Will be ignored
Collections	access_description	ADDITION	We will replace the access_description fields for a new field,access_description (without sample,data or image).	Yes	Will be ignored
Collections	access_uri	ADDITION	We will replace the access_uri fields for a new field,access_uri (without sample,data or image).	Yes	Will be ignored
Collections	sample_access_fee	DELETE	No longer necessary when the field, sample is already in field "access_fee"	Yes	Will be ignored
Collections	sample_access_joint_project	DELETE	No longer necessary when the field, sample is already in field "joint_projects"	Yes	Will be ignored
Collections	sample_access_description	DELETE	No longer necessary when the field, sample is already in field "access_description"	No	Will be ignored
Collections	sample_access_uri	DELETE	No longer necessary when the field, sample is already in field "access_uri"	No	Will be ignored
Collections	data_access_fee	DELETE	No longer necessary when the field, data is already in field "access_fee"	Yes	Will be ignored
Collections	data_access_joint_project	DELETE	No longer necessary when the field, data is already in field "access_joint_projects"	Yes	Will be ignored
Collection	data_access_description	DELETE	No longer necessary when the field, data is already in field "access_description"	No	Will be ignored

Collection	<i>data_access_uri</i>	DELETE	No longer necessary when the field, data is already in field "access_uri"	No	Will be ignored
Collection	<i>image_access_fee</i>	DELETE	No longer necessary when the field, image is already in field "access_fee"	Yes	Will be ignored
Collection	<i>image_joint_project</i>	DELETE	No longer necessary when the field, image is already in field "access_joint_projects"	Yes	Will be ignored
Collection	<i>image_access_description</i>	DELETE	No longer necessary when the field, data is already in field "access_description"	No	Will be ignored
Collection	<i>image_access_uri</i>	DELETE	No longer necessary when the field, image is already in field "access_uri"	No	Will be ignored
Collection	<i>sop</i>	ADDITION	We will replace the sample_sop fields for a Mref field, sample_sop (without processing,transport or storage), A new table "sop" is needed (see below). Here you can chose : processing,transport, storage)	No	Will be ignored
Collection	<i>sample_processing_sop</i>	DELETE	No longer necessary because of the field "sample_sop".	No	Will be ignored
Collection	<i>sample_transport_sop</i>	DELETE	No longer necessary because of the field "sample_sop".	No	Will be ignored
Collection	<i>sample_storage_sop</i>	DELETE	No longer necessary because of the field "sample_sop".	No	Will be ignored
Collection	<i>processing_sop</i>	ADDITION	We will replace the data_sop fields for a Mref field, data_sop (without processing,transport or storage), A new table "sop" is needed (see below). Here you can chose : processing,transport, storage)	No	Will be ignored
Collection	<i>data_processing_sop</i>	DELETE	No longer necessary because of the field "data_sop".	No	Will be ignored
Collection	<i>data_transport_sop</i>	DELETE	No longer necessary because of the field "data_sop".	No	Will be ignored
Collection	<i>data_storage_sop</i>	DELETE	No longer necessary because of the field "data_sop".	No	Will be ignored

Appendix 2 – new needed tables and table changes

Table “access” (categories)

<i>Table</i>	<i>Name</i>
<i>Access</i>	<i>sample</i>
<i>Access</i>	<i>data</i>
<i>Access</i>	<i>image</i>

Table “sop” (categories)

<i>Table</i>	<i>Name</i>
<i>sop</i>	<i>Sample processing</i>
<i>sop</i>	<i>Sample transport</i>
<i>sop</i>	<i>Sample storage</i>
<i>sop</i>	<i>Data processing</i>
<i>sop</i>	<i>Data transport</i>
<i>sop</i>	<i>Data storage</i>